

8TH EDITION

THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY

TÎRGU MUREȘ

19-20 OCTOBER 2024

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CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

SATURDAY- 19 OCTOBER 2024

- **Literature**
- **Language and Discourse**
- **Communication, Journalism, Education Sciences, Psychology and Sociology**
- **History, Political Sciences, International Relations**
- **Social Sciences**

The conference is organised in partnership by:

*"Alpha" Institute for Multicultural Studies
"Gh. Șincai" Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities
"Dimitrie Cantemir" University of Tîrgu Mureș*

A WORD FROM THE PRESIDENT OF THE CONFERENCE

Dear Guests,

Having established a certain tradition in the recent years, the International Conference *COMMUNICATION, CONTEXT, INTERDISCIPLINARITY* (now at its 8th edition) intends to unite emerging scholars, as well as prestigious researchers from different fields of radical relevance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. Literature, the cultural discours as well as the arts gain new connections and dimensions through fundamental changes and structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research becomes extremely important. It is a fact that in our postmodern times, we live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life, but to the risks and dangers of which we are at the same time exposed. *Non scholae sed vitae discimus* (*We do not learn for the school, but for life*) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. It is essential that the path between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this interesting and captivating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting

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works and papers, together with ideas generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

I wish to express my hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

Prof. IULIAN BOLDEA, PhD
President of the *CCI 8* Conference

SATURDAY – 19 OCTOBER 2024

LITERATURE

Moderators: Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD, UMFST Tîrgu Mureş; Prof. Ştefan Lucian Mureşanu, PhD, „Hyperion” University of Bucharest; Scientific Researcher Nicoleta Sălcudeanu, PhD, „Gheorghe Şincai” Institute for Social Sciences, Târgu Mureş

1. Iulian Boldea, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureş, *MEMORY, CONFESSION AND DESTINY IN THE WORK OF VARUJAN VOSGANIAN*
2. Ştefan Lucian Mureşanu, Prof., PhD, „Hyperion” University of Bucharest, *MEANING AND ESTHETIC ENJOYMENT IN HORACE’S ODES FROM “THE THIRD BOOK”*
3. Nicoleta Sălcudeanu, Scientific Researcher, PhD, „Gheorghe Şincai” Institute for Social Sciences, Târgu Mureş, *MARIN MINCU – A TENDER OVEREMOTIONAL POLEMICIST*
4. Iulian Băicuş, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *I HAVE BEEN TO NEW CHINA*
5. Iudit Călinescu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Szeged, *INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL EXILE IN THE NOVELS “THE FRENCH TESTAMENT”, BY ANDREÏ MAKINE AND “GOOD NIGHT, CHILDREN!”, BY RADU PAVEL GHEO*
6. Călina Paliciuc, Lecturer, PhD, „Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad, *MANIFESTATIONS AND EVOLUTION OF THE FANTASTIC IN WORLD LITERATURE*
7. Maria Laţchici, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *ASPECTS OF IVO VOJNOVIC'S DRAMATURGY*

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8. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering, Bucharest, *EGYPTIAN CULTURE IN CLAUDIA MILLIAN'S POEMS NOCTURA EGIPTIANA (EGYPTIAN NIGHT) AND PISICILE (THE CATS)*
9. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering, Bucharest, *AN ANALYSIS OF THE POEM SIMFONIA TACERII (THE SYMPHONY OF SILENCE) BY CLAUDIA MILLIAN*
10. Lucreția-Dorina Loghin, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *STORY AND HISTORY IN KEN FOLLETT'S TRILOGIES*
11. Mihaela-Anca Ogasanu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, *PSYCHOLOGICAL, MORAL AND GENDER ISSUES IN A CLASSIC AMERICAN „GIRLS' BOOK”*
12. Ruxandra Coman, Lecturer, PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” Christian University, Bucharest, *THE HONESTY OF THE AUTHOR. STYLISTIC MEANS AND NARRATIVE TECHNIQUES IN LIVIU REBREANU'S SHORT PROSE*
13. Simona Olaru-Poșiar, Lecturer, PhD, "Victor Babeș" University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Timișoara, "C-CLASC" Centre of Applied Linguistics and Comparative Cultural Studies, *THE WITCH MUST DIE- THE NEED FOR (FAIRY) TALES IN TODAY'S DIGITAL SOCIETY*
14. Adela Catană, Lecturer, PhD, „Ferdinand I” Military Technical Academy, *“A LARGE MIRROR”: RECOLLECTIONS OF THE “DOUBLE” IN EDGAR ALLAN POE'S “WILLIAM WILSON” AND “LIGEIA”*
15. Anda Dimitriu, Assist. Prof., PhD, Junior Lecturer, University of Bucharest, *THE EXOTIC AND THE FAMILIAR: TRANSLATING FEMALE IDENTITY FOR THE BIG SCREEN*
16. Monica-Alina Toma, Assist. Prof., PhD, University of Economic Studies, Bucharest, *THE POETICS OF*

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FEMININITY IN NICHITA STĂNESCU'S ACCLAIMED BOOK, A VISION OF FEELINGS (1964)

17. Alexandra-Maria Vrînceanu, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *ADAPTING HORROR FICTION AS FILMS FOR NEW GENERATIONS: THE RECEPTION OF THE FEAR STREET TRILOGY ON NETFLIX*
18. Camelia Ioana Ienciu (Popa), PhD, *AN OVERALL CONTEXT OF KATE MORTON'S THE FORGOTTEN GARDEN*
19. Denisa Elena Duna, PhD, *CAUSES OF THE DECLINE OF PENINSULAR PEOPLES. CULTURAL REFORM AND COUNTER-REFORM*
20. Georgiana Elisabeta Panait (Baciu), PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *NICOLAE VELEA - CHRONOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES*
21. Anca Rusu, PhD Student, UMFST „G.E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *PAUL ZARIFOPOL. THE TRANSFIGURED JOURNEY THROUGH LITERATURE*
22. Diana-Mihaela Sofian, PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE RAMSHACKLE ELEVATOR IN THE IVORY TOWER*
23. Camelia Bof (Hreban), PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *THE INITIATORY JOURNEY. PERSPECTIVES*
24. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *EUGÈNE IONESCO'S BATTLE TO THE DEATH. A MISUNDERSTANDING OF THE CONCEPT OF LIFE IN CONTEMPORANEITY. A LITERARY PERSPECTIVE OF THE DEATH IN 'EXIT THE KING' MASTERPIECE*
25. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE UNDERSTANDING OF ARGHEZI LITERARY WORKS BY THE LENS OF EUGÈNE IONESCO POETIC VISIONARY*

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FORCES. A CRITICAL PERCEPTION OF THE INTER-WAR LITERARY POET DUHOVNICEASCA AND THE DEMOLITION OF ROMANIAN VALUES DURING THE INTER-WAR PERIOD

26. Ozana-Ioana Ciobanu, PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *FROM MACONDO TO METROPOLIS*
27. Ingrid Nistor-Sopon, PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *WAR AND DECONSTRUCTION IN BERTOLT BRECHTS „MANN IST MANN“*
28. Rebeca-Daniela Stănescu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Center, *URMUZ AND LEWIS CARROLL- TURN IN THE MIRROR WORLD*
29. Silvia-Ofelia Chelariu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, *MIHAI EMINESCU. VISUAL EXPRESSION*
30. Adriana Maria Călugăr (Cutean), PhD Student, „1 Decembrie 1918 ” University of Alba Iulia, *REPRESENTATIVE WRITERS OF MEMOIRS FROM PRE-COMMUNIST DETENTION IN ROMANIA*
31. Anca Pînzariu (Boldea), PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *THE READING OF HOLY BOOKS IN ROMANIAN INTERWAR NOVELS*
32. Carmen-Ancuța Morari, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *ÉVA HEYMAN. CONFIGURATIONS OF CRISIS IN THE HOLOCAUST DIARY*
33. Andreea-Corina Batori, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *A LUGGAGE AS BIG AS A COUNTRY – IN AGLAJA’S VETERANYI “RAFTUL CU ULTIMELE SUFLĂRI”*

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34. Oana Loredana Bițu (Diaconu), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Center, *THE RELATION BETWEEN IMAGINARY AND OBJECTOLOGY IN ZAHARIA STANCU'S POETRY*
35. Cristina-Daniela Lateș, PhD Student, UMFST „G.E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *NARRATIVE AS THE ARCHITECT OF MEANING IN FIRESC BY PETRU CIMPOEȘU*
36. Diana-Ioana Faur (Feurdean), PhD Student, UMFST „G.E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *SEMANTIC FIELDS OF SILENCE OF THE WORLD/ SILENCE OF THE HUMAN BEING IN LUCIAN BLAGA'S LYRIC*
37. Laurențiu Boșog, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE APOCALYPTIC ITALIANS OF ELIZABETHAN LITERATURE*
38. Mihaela Sandu (Hură), PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *OVIDIU BÎRLEA – MONOGRAPHIC ITINERARY*
39. Mirela-Cristina Coman (Liuță), PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *MIGRATION, BETWEEN RESILIENCE AND UPROOTING. HUMAN BEING WITHOUT COUNTRY*
40. Miriam-Christéle Gardner-Nedelcu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *IRISH VICTORIAN WOMEN TRAVELLERS TO ITALY: LADY MORGAN*
41. Ioan Alexandru Murar, PhD Student, University of Pitești, *THE NARRATOR'S IDENTITY - EXISTENTIAL DOUBLE OR EXISTENTIAL DOUBLING AS A LIMINAL STATE IN JON FOSSE'S THE OTHER NAME (SEPTOLOGY I-II)*
42. Constantin-Andrei Pătrăucean, PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *THE HUTSULS,*

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TODAY- STARTING POINT OF A NECESSARY ETNOGRAPHIC RESEARCH

43. Roxana-Maria Sînescu, PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *LUCIAN BLAGA’S DRAMATURGY, A FERTILE REALM FOR THEATRICAL PRODUCTIONS*
44. Anamaria Valentina Ungur, PhD Student, North University Centre of Baia Mare, *IOAN GROȘAN- A HUMOR FIGURE OF COMMUNIST TIMES*
45. Maria-Loredana Simionovici (Grosariu), PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *IDENTITÄTSPROBLEMATIK IN HERMANN HESSES ENTWICKLUNGSROMAN DER STEPPENWOLF*

SATURDAY – 19 OCTOBER 2024

LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE

Moderators: Prof. Floriana Popescu, PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați; Lecturer Marta-Teodora Boboc, PhD, University of Bucharest; Lecturer Cristina Furtună, PhD, “Valahia” University of Târgoviște

1. Floriana Popescu, Prof., PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *EPONYMISMS ARE A PRECIOUS LEGACY*
2. Ioana-Crina Prodan, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *LINGUISTIC AND SEMIOTIC PECULIARITIES OF SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE*
3. Lizeta-Cristina Furtună, Lecturer, PhD, „Valahia” University of Târgoviște, *FORMS OF LEISURE IN THE NOVELS OF NICOLAE BREBAN (DON JUAN AND BUNAVESTIRE)*
4. Cristina-Dana Popescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *THE ENACTMENT OF LEGAL TRIAL SIMULATIONS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING: AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH*
5. Loredana Liliana Buzoianu, Lecturer, PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *THE CONCEPT OF TRANSFORMATION. WAYS OF CONTRACTION*
6. Loredana Liliana Buzoianu, Lecturer, PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *THE CONCEPT OF TRANSFORMATION. WAYS OF EXPANSION*
7. Marta-Teodora Boboc, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *A PRAGMATIC APPROACH TO SPECIALISED VOCABULARY IN TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS*

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8. Iustina Nica, Scientific Researcher II, PhD, "C.S. Nicolăescu-Plopșor" Scientific Research Institute, Romanian Academy, Craiova, *THE PRESENCE OF THE WORD "SUDIT" IN ROMANIAN TOPONYMY AND ANTHROPONYMY*
9. Alexandra Moldovan, PhD Student, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *LINGUISTIC CHALLENGES IN SOURCE TEXT ANALYSIS AND TARGET TEXT REVISION WITH SPEECH SYNTHESIS*
10. Andrei-Ionuț Popa, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *FOLK ETIMOLOGY IN RELATION TO LEXICAL DISTORSION AND PARONYMIC ATTRACTION*
11. Marta-Cristiana Burghiu (Negraia), PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *THE PROCESS OF REFUTATION IN THE REPRESENTATION OF MUSLIM WOMEN IN THE FRENCH WRITTEN PRESS*
12. Violeta Marinela Dumitru (Preduț), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Pitești University Center, *INFLUENCES OF FASHION LANGUAGE ON COMMON VOCABULARY*

SATURDAY – 19 OCTOBER 2024

***COMMUNICATION, JOURNALISM, EDUCATION
SCIENCES, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIOLOGY***

Moderators: Prof. Teodor Pătrăuță, PhD, "Vasile Goldiș" Western University of Arad; Assoc. Prof. Angelica Hobjilă, PhD, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași; Assoc. Prof. Laura Ioana Leon, PhD, "Grigore T. Popa" University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iași

1. Teodor Pătrăuță, Prof., PhD, "Vasile Goldiș" Western University of Arad, *NEW EDUCATIONAL PARADIGM VERSUS MODERN EDUCATION*
2. Nelu Vicol, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *A CONCEPTUAL AND COMPREHENSIVE DESIGN: WHO AND WHAT THEY LEARN*
3. Angelica Hobjilă, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, *COMMUNICATION IN LITERARY CONTEXT: READING LOGS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL*
4. Laura Ioana Leon, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Grigore T. Popa" University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iași, *THE INTERSECTION OF FOOD AND CULTURE IN THE DINNER TABLE (2023)*
5. Maria Pleșca, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *EXISTENTIAL VALUES - KEY TO TEACHERS' WELL-BEING*
6. Adrian Păcurar, Lecturer, PhD, "Vasile Goldiș" Western University of Arad, Lia Lucia Epure, Assoc. Prof., PhD, "Vasile Goldiș" Western University of Arad, *ROMANIAN*

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PSYCHOLOGY DURING THE COMMUNIST REGIME BETWEEN COMPLETE FAILURE AND SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCY. AUTHORS AND CULTURAL PERSPECTIVES

7. Alexandra Georgiana Sălcianu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Science and Technology Politehnica, Bucharest, *SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PARTICULARITIES OF AN INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH IN THE DOMAINS OF MARKETING/ADVERTISING AND LITERARY CREATION*
8. Mădălina Gabriela Ionescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Valahia” University of Târgoviște, *THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC THEORY, SOLFEGGIO AND DICTATION IN THE FORMATION OF THE MUSICAL SKILLS OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN NURSERY, PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY EDUCATION*
9. Adela Sava (Codreș), PhD, University of Craiova, *CHALLENGES OF LITERARY TEXTS IN THE FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSROOM*
10. István Péter, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *PAID INTERNSHIP – LONG TERM SOLUTION FOR WORKING STUDENTS?*
11. Corina Lilioara Lung, PhD Student, clinical psychologist, State University of Moldova, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *PSYCHOPATHOLOGICAL COMORBIDITIES ASSOCIATED WITH CHRONIC INFLAMMATORY DISEASES IN ADULTS*
12. Mariana Suciaghi, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, Principal Clinical Psychologist, couple and family psychotherapist, Târgu Mureș County Emergency Clinical Hospital, Romania, ATI Clinical Department, Individual Psychology Office Suciaghi Mariana,

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*METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ACUTE STRESS IN
INTENSIVE CARE PATIENTS*

13. Mihaela Sandu, PhD Student, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chişinău, Republic of Moldova, *ASPECTS OF MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES IN PRESCHOOL*

SATURDAY – 19 OCTOBER 2024

**HISTORY, POLITICAL SCIENCES, INTERNATIONAL
RELATIONS**

*Moderators: Prof. Cornel Sigmirean, PhD, UMFST Tîrgu Mureş;
Assoc. Prof. Fănel Teodoraşcu, PhD, Danubius International
University of Galaţi; Prof. Ioana-Iulia Olaru, PhD, „G. Enescu”
National University of Arts, Iaşi*

1. Cornel Sigmirean, Prof. PhD, UMFST Tîrgu Mureş, *LATINITY AS AN IDENTITY ELEMENT AMONG ROMANIANS IN TRAANSILVANIA. A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE*
2. Ioana-Iulia Olaru, Prof., PhD, „G. Enescu” National University of Arts, Iaşi, *INNOVATIONS IN THE PALEOLITHIC PAINTING: SUBJECTS, TECHNIQUES AND MATERIALS*
3. Fănel Teodoraşcu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Danubius International University of Galaţi, *THE PRESS UNDERSTOOD AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR EDUCATING THE PEOPLE. SOME OPINIONS FROM THE PAST*
4. Arthur Mihăilă, Lecturer, PhD, ”Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE SHIFTING GLOBAL POWER DYNAMICS: AN ANALYSIS OF CHINA’S RISE, RUSSIA’S ASSERTIVENESS, AND THE CHANGING SPHERES OF INFLUENCE*
5. Patricia-Dorli Dumescu, Lecturer, PhD, „Victor Babeş” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Timișoara, „C-CLASC” Centre for Applied Linguistics and Comparative Cultural Studies, *THE HAND OF DA VINCI*

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6. Maria Costea, Scientific Researcher, PhD, Romanian Academy's Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities „Gheorghe Șincai” Târgu Mureș and Simion Costea, Senior Lecturer, PhD, Global Governance Institute, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVES ON THE EU'S CRITERIA FOR CANDIDATE COUNTRIES*
7. Tatiana Scurtu, Scientific Researcher, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities of the Romanian Academy, Târgu Mureș, *THE DOCUMENTS OF THE SZEKLER BORDER REGIMENTS IN THE COVASNA COUNTY BUREAU OF THE NATIONAL ARCHIVES OF ROMANIA*
8. Corina Mașca, Novice Researcher, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities of the Romanian Academy, *PATHS OF POWER: THE EVOLUTION OF THE ROMANIAN COMMUNIST PARTY IN MUREȘ, 1944-1945*
9. Ferencz Iozsef Truța, Research Assistant, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities of the Romanian Academy, Târgu Mureș, *JOHN D. ROCKEFELLER IN THE INTER-WAR ROMANIAN PRESS. THE FASCINATION OF MILLIONS*
10. Narcis-Mihai Martiniuc, Research Assistant, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences, Târgu Mureș, *„ROMÂNUL TÂRNĂVEAN” JOURNAL: DAILY LIFE, POLITICS AND MENTALITIES, 1910-1914*
11. Florentina Trif, PhD, „Gavrilă Simion” Institute of Eco-Museal Research, Tulcea, *SOME REFLECTIONS ON THE CONVENTION REGARDING THE PROTECTION OF THE WORLD CULTURAL AND NATURAL HERITAGE*

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12. Ștefan Colbu, PhD, „Mihai Eminescu” Central University Library of Iași, *IMMIGRATION AND THE STATE – CHALLENGES FOR THE HOST SOCIETY*
13. Bogdan Iulian Ranteș, PhD, „Valahia” University of Târgoviște, *ROMANIA'S CULTURAL AND SCIENTIFIC RELATIONS WITH THE FORMER FRENCH COLONIES IN NORTH AFRICA: ALGERIA, MOROCCO, TUNISIA (1956-1970)*
14. József Gyenge, PhD, „Domokos Kázmér” Technological High School, Sovata, Secondary School Sărățeni, *THE CONCORDAT BETWEEN THE HOLY SEE AND THE KINGDOM OF ROMANIA*
15. Mihai Cristian Neagu, PhD, University of Bucharest, *FUNERARY SITES OF THE CERNAVODA II CULTURE DISCOVERED AT OLTENIȚA, COUNTY OF CĂLĂRAȘI*
16. Vasile-Virgil Coman, PhD, *FROM THE YEARS OF CONSERVATIVE GOVERNMENT (1871-1876)*
17. Liviu Olteanu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE SYMBOLISM OF FUNERARY RITES. ANCIENT PRACTICES. APPOINTED TIMES FOR REMEMBRANCE (COMMEMORATION OF THE DEAD)*
18. Marinel Pădure, PhD Student, „Ovidius” University of Constanța, *SACRED ART IN THE 18TH CENTURY IN MUNTENIA BETWEEN THE TRADITIONAL PAST AND THE CHALLENGES OF THE FUTURE*
19. Andrei Mic, PhD Student, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *NICOLAE IORGA AND THE TRANSYLVANIAN HISTORICAL WRITING. CASE STUDIES: NEAMUL ROMÂNESC ÎN ARDEAL ȘI ȚARA UNGUREASCĂ (1906); SCRISORI ȘI INSCRIPTII ARDELENE ȘI MARAMUREȘENE (1906). ANALYSIS AND PERCEPTIONS*

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20. Ana-Monica Crăciuneanu, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *PATTERNS OF MEDICEAN GEM PREFERENCES IN SIXTEENTH CENTURY FLORENCE*

SATURDAY – 19 OCTOBER 2024

SOCIAL SCIENCES

Moderators: Prof. Lucreția Dogaru, PhD, UMFST Târgu Mureș; Assoc. Prof. Silviu Gabriel Barbu, PhD, „Transilvania” University of Brașov; Lecturer Niadi-Corina Cernica, PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava

1. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *CIVIL LAW AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH OTHER BRANCHES OF LAW*
2. Lucreția Dogaru, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *THE QUALITY OF VICE OF CONSENT THAT THE INJURY HAS*
3. Silviu Gabriel Barbu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Transilvania” University of Brașov and Alexandru Petruț Constantin, MA Student, police officer, General Inspectorate of the Romanian Police, *SHORT OBSERVATIONS ON THE CRIMINAL STATUTE OF LIMITATIONS IN EU MEMBER STATES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR JUDICIAL COOPERATION*
4. Niadi-Corina Cernica, Lecturer, PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *MONAD AS PSYCHICAL ENTITY IN WORK OF LEIBNIZ*
5. Georgiana Chițiga, Scientific Researcher, „Victor Slăvescu” Centre for Financial and Monetary Research, Romanian Academy, *FINANCING CLIMATE NEUTRALITY AT EU LEVEL*
6. Narcisa Maria Mitu, Scientific Researcher III, PhD, “C. S. Nicolăescu-Plopșor” Institute for Research in Social Studies and Humanities, Craiova, *SUCCESSFUL ENTREPRENEURS FROM CRAIOVA’S PAST (LATE 19TH CENTURY-EARLY 20TH CENTURY). BRIEF BIOGRAPHICAL PRESENTATIONS*

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